

SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE CULTURE AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this research paper it is analyzed that students' lifestyle showed the need to develop and carry out preventive and sanitary-educational work to eliminate and correct the identified negative trends. Mastering this profession requires not only the assimilation of a certain amount of knowledge and skills, it presupposes a certain attitude in life, makes high demands on the personal qualities of a person, and not least to his physical and mental health. In the modern conditions of social, environmental, economic and political instability of our society, student youth are under significant pressure from society and environment. The widespread introduction of innovative technologies also has a significant impact on the rhythm of human life and his psychological state.*

Keywords: *culture of healthy lifestyle, educational and professional work, medical students, rules and criteria.*

INTRODUCTION

At present, in our country, citizens' commitment to the culture of health is not favorable. The influence of risk factors can be reduced by active actions to promote a healthy lifestyle and prevent diseases, both at the federal and regional levels. An important role in this direction is played by educational work among the population in order to increase their awareness of the need for a responsible attitude to their own health, which health specialists are called upon to ensure. Person's physical well-being depends to a large extent on mastering the skills of a healthy lifestyle, which can prevent the development of many diseases. The health of students is of great social and medical importance, since they have to implement such important social functions of society as professional labor, reproductive, intellectual, moral, etc. tasks of professional activity of which is the formation of the moral and physical health of our society. A doctor needs to inform every resident of our country about a healthy lifestyle, preventive measures, as well as the correct treatment of already identified diseases. It should be quickly and easily explained what exactly everyone can do to maintain their health. Mastering this profession requires not only the assimilation of a certain amount of knowledge and skills, it presupposes a certain attitude in life, makes high demands on the personal qualities of a person, and not least to his physical and mental health. In the modern conditions of social, environmental, economic and political instability of our society, student youth are under significant pressure from society and environment. The widespread introduction of innovative technologies also has a significant impact on the rhythm of human life and his psychological state. Successful training of highly qualified personnel is closely related to the promotion and maintenance of health. Health is a qualitative prerequisite for the future self-realization of young people, the ability to create a family and bear children, to difficult educational and professional work, social, political and creative activity. In modern conditions, health ceases to be only a personal matter of a young person, since it becomes a factor in the

survival of society as a whole. Therefore, protecting the health of students is considered one of the most important social tasks of society. Particular relevance for the implementation of this task is the formation of a healthy lifestyle among young people. Healthy lifestyle conveys the completeness of a person's involvement in various forms and methods of social activity, according to the optimal and harmonious development of all his structures: bodily, mental, social, and includes all components of various activities aimed at protecting and improving the health of young people. A healthy lifestyle is not limited to individual forms of medical and social activity: the eradication of bad habits, adherence to hygiene standards and rules, health education, seeking treatment or advice from medical institutions, adherence to work, rest, nutrition and many others, although they all reflect certain aspects of it. Along with the introduction of new technologies for prevention and treatment, it is necessary to pay special attention to the creation of motivations and conditions for a healthy lifestyle.

PURPOSE OF WORK

The purpose of this article is to analyze and identify the problems of a healthy lifestyle of medical students. To find ways to solve them, to develop conclusions and recommendations on a healthy lifestyle for students of medical universities.

METHODS

Working with literature and theoretical analysis.

DISCUSSION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

The aim of the study was to analyze the lifestyle of students of Tashkent Pediatric Institute in order to draw up practical recommendations on the formation of the need for a healthy lifestyle in order to maintain and strengthen health.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set:

1. to study students' awareness of the concept and principles of a healthy lifestyle;
2. to study the main characteristics of nutrition, sleep and other elements of the way of life and their hygienic assessment;
3. to develop measures to create a need for a healthy lifestyle among students.

The study involved 150 students, the method of questioning (author's questionnaire), analytical and statistical methods were used.

We found that 88% of students understand the importance of a healthy lifestyle, but only half of them know the main components that characterize it and only a third can name the basic principles of rational nutrition, organization of good rest and sleep. When asked about the observance of the rules of a healthy lifestyle, 65% of students noted that due to the heavy workload and lack of free time associated with a busy study schedule, they often pay insufficient attention to nutrition, healthy sleep, physical activity, etc. Rational nutrition is an integral part of individual human health, which takes a significant part in the development of physical, mental and social well-being. Nutrition has the greatest impact on human health. According to experts from the World Health Organization, 40% of all diseases are associated with malnutrition. Our physical health, immunity, longevity, mental harmony all of this is directly related to the problem of healthy human nutrition. We have found that the organization of healthy food is one of the most pressing problems of medical students. So, according to the results of the study, it was revealed that 45% of the respondents consider their food to be wrong, but in fact, the food of about 65% of the respondents does not meet hygienic standards. The students revealed the following deficiencies in the diet and nutrition:

- discrepancy between the energy value of the diet and energy consumption in 37% of students;

- inconsistency of the ratio of proteins: fats, carbohydrates with hygienic standards (50%);
- lack of minerals and vitamins, primarily calcium, phosphorus, fat-soluble vitamins A, E, as well as water-soluble vitamin C (45%);

- a monotonous diet, while 35% of respondents do not eat fish at all, and 17% - grain products.

- 50% of students eat fast food. The most popular among these products were: street food (16% of students), cereals and instant soups (12%) and snacks (9%).

- the presence in the diet of every second student of a large amount of simple carbohydrates (bakery and confectionery products, sweet carbonated and energy drinks);

- 54% of students do not comply with the required time intervals and the distribution of calories between individual meals;

- a significant number of students (49%) do not have a full breakfast and lunch in terms of qualitative and quantitative characteristics and try to compensate for this with an excessively dense, high-calorie and unbalanced dinner;

- only 9% of respondents eat first courses every day.

The main reasons for this situation among students are:

- insufficient awareness of students about the basic principles of rational nutrition;

- high density of the study load, which leads to fatigue and unwillingness of students to cook full meals;

- lack of time for cooking due to the long duration of the school day and the presence of many circles and electives, without which quality teaching and mastering practical skills is impossible;

- short breaks between classes, the need for frequent travel during the day do not allow students to have a full meal;

- unwillingness to bring home-cooked food for a number of psychological and behavioral attitudes that have developed in their environment;

- 35% of students noted insufficient material support;

- for students living in dormitories, the process of cooking itself becomes a big problem due to the lack of equipment, or its constant use by other residents,

- for 12% of first-year students, psychological factors are of great importance - unusual sanitary conditions, a large number of people watching the cooking process, fear of public condemnation due to inability to cook and etc.

The data obtained indicate that the majority of the interviewed students have a high risk of developing diseases of various organs and systems, primarily the pathology of the gastrointestinal tract, at a young age. It is alarming that among the respondents there are already persons who have acquired chronic diseases or problems associated with the gastrointestinal tract. So, 17% of the respondents were diagnosed with chronic gastritis, 3% - chronic duodenitis and 9%, although they do not have any diseases, still complain of recurrent dyspeptic symptoms. In addition to deficiencies in the quality and organization of food, the majority of students recorded a lack of sleep, a discrepancy between the daily routine and biological rhythms, a sedentary lifestyle, and the presence of bad habits (smoking and drinking alcoholic beverages). It was revealed that the majority of students are aware that they have a discrepancy between their lifestyle and the

principles and criteria of a healthy lifestyle. In addition to the lack of control over their diet, which is the main aspect of the development of a healthy lifestyle, students have many factors that exacerbate the impact of lifestyle on human health: smoking, drinking alcohol and energy drinks, a sedentary lifestyle and disturbed sleep and wakefulness. Many individuals wish to maintain a healthy lifestyle, but do not, citing psychological difficulties in connection with the difficult educational process and personal circumstances. It was found that the overwhelming majority of students simply do not know all the rules and criteria for a healthy lifestyle, therefore they do not fulfill them or do them incorrectly. Also, a significant part of students point to the acute shortage of time as the reason for non-compliance with a healthy lifestyle, which is both a psychological factor and a physical one. However, in some courses of study, the schedule allows to allocate free time to take care of health, and at the same time, students cannot correctly draw up their schedule and need proper time management.

RESULTS

The analysis of students' lifestyle showed the need to develop and carry out preventive and sanitary-educational work to eliminate and correct the identified negative trends. To do this, we conducted conversations with students on the topics: "Healthy lifestyle and youth health", "Rational nutrition and ways of organizing it for students", "How to organize your day correctly", "Energize in the morning", "Energy drinks - admission rules", "Prepare yourself for sleep". The correct plan of the working day was drawn up according to the schedule of students, depending on the course, information leaflets with norms and recommendations for maintaining a healthy lifestyle were developed and distributed among students in printed form. This method can help young people remember that their health is the key to their future success, and what they need to do to achieve it.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, main directions of using health-improving activities for students should be focused on observing the daily regimen, combating harmful habits, negative emotions, and increasing physical activity.

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